

Full-scale Demonstration of Replicable Technologies for Hydrogen Combustion in Hard to Abate Industries: The Aluminium use-case

M. Lubrano Lavadera

Aero-Thermo-Mechanics Department, Université Libre de Bruxelles, 1050 Bruxelles, Belgium

Background

By 2030, gas burners and furnaces units in **hard-to-abate industries** (HTAIs) must be equipped to run on 100% H₂ and meet the same NO_x emissions standards as gas burners. To achieve H₂ full potential, there are **several challenges** that must be addressed:

1. Different combustion properties
2. Pollutant emissions
3. Quality of the product
4. Accelerated wear of furnace's components
5. Safety
6. Lack of training
7. Lack of confidence regarding scalability and business potential

Objectives and ambition

1. To understand and characterize the H₂ combustion and its effects on the process.
2. To develop a burner able to run on 100% H₂ and H₂/NG mixtures whilst respecting the NO_x emissions.
3. To retrofit a furnace with the developed burner, optimal refractory materials, sensing solutions, to enable the efficient application of H₂ combustion in industrial applications.
4. Full-scale demonstration of the technologies developed in the aluminium industry.
5. To implement Standard Operating Procedures on safety and plant integration procedures.
6. To assess the impact of shifting a conventional industrial process to a H₂-based system.
7. To develop and promote new business models for a wide exploitation of H₂-based solutions in HTAIs.

The Consortium

1. Université Libre de Bruxelles (Belgium)
2. 2A SpA (Italy)
3. Nippon Gases Industrial SRL (Italy)
4. Fraunhofer (Germany)
5. Tecnalia Research & Innovation (Spain)
6. GHI Hornos Industriales, SRL (Spain)
7. Gas- und Wärme-Institut Essen e. V. (Germany)
8. BlueEnergy Revolution (Italy)
9. EKW Refractories GmbH (Germany)
10. European Aluminium (Belgium)

Specific methodologies

Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD)

Experimental Techniques

Overall methodology

